

Fungicidal screening : The compounds were screened for antifungal activity against *A. flavus*, *H. oryzae* and *C. sacchari* by agar plate technique^{1,2} at three different concentrations, viz. 1000, 100 and 10 ppm. Two commercial fungicides Memege and Blitox 50 WP were also tested under similar conditions to compare the result. The number of replication in each case was three. The percentage inhibition of growth of fungus colony is given by the following expression.

$$\text{Percentage inhibition} = \frac{C-T}{C} \times 100$$

where C=diameter of fungus colony (mm) in control after 96 h,

T=diameter of fungus colony (mm) in presence of test chemical after 96 h.

Results and Discussion

Most of the compounds screened possess moderate to fairly good level of fungicidal activity against all the three fungi showing more activity against *C. sacchari*. Introduction of different groups and their position did not affect the toxicity to any marked degree. However, compounds containing CH₃ group were found to be more active than the unsubstituted compounds.

A comparison of thiazolyl compounds (Tables 1-4) shows the following order of antifungal activity.

compounds IV > compounds III > compounds II > compounds I. Highly active compounds of the series contain a thiazolyl and a triazolyl moiety.

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Alkaloid Contents of *Lupinus hartwegii* Roots

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LUPINUS hartwegii (Leguminosae), an annual herb, is a highly crossbred cultivar grown in gardens as winter ornamental^{1,2}. The plant has been investigated earlier by different workers for quinolizidine alkaloids³⁻⁵. No work has been reported so far on the roots of this species.

The present work deals with the isolation and characterisation of three quinolizidine and one indole alkaloid from the CHCl₃ extract of *L. hartwegii* roots.

Completely air dried and coarsely ground roots (500 g) were exhaustively extracted in a soxhlet extractor successively with petroleum ether (60-80°) and ethanol (95%). The ethanol extract was worked up with CHCl₃ by the usual procedure for the isolation of alkaloids⁶. The CHCl₃ extract, on column chromatography over neutral Al₂O₃ gave four alkaloids (compounds A-D), which were visualised on tlc plates by spraying iodoplatinate reagent⁶.

Compound A (aphylline) was crystallised from petroleum ether as colourless needles (30 mg), m.p. 99-101° (Lit.⁷ m.p. 100-101°); perchlorate, m.p. 233°; ν_{max} (KBr)⁸ 2970, 1640, 1455 and 1280 cm⁻¹; m/e^9 248 (M⁺), 247, 220, 137, 136, 98, 97, 96 and 84.

Compound B (lupanine) was crystallised from petroleum ether as colourless flakes (175 mg), m.p. 97-98°; perchlorate, m.p. 224°; co-tlc, m.m.p. and superimposable ir with an authentic sample confirmed the identity^{2,10}.

Compound C (nuttaline) was crystallised from acetone as colourless needles (35 mg), m.p. 107-109° (Lit.¹¹ m.p. 108-109°); perchlorate, m.p. 170-172°; ν_{max} (KBr)¹¹ 3480, 2810, 2760, 1650 and 1012 cm⁻¹; m/e^{12} 264 (M⁺), 246, 236, 154, 153, 152, 123, 84 and 55.

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Compound D (gramine) was crystallised from acetone as colourless needles (60 mg), m.p. 134°; perchlorate, m.p. 150-151°; identified^{1,5} by direct comparison with an authentic sample.

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An Efficient Method for Estimation of Trace Level Mercury in Chlor-alkali Effluents

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THE high toxicity of mercury and its presence in many unsuspected sources have prompted many workers to recommend methods to eliminate the sources of its contamination or to reduce its content maximally. In recent years there has been considerable interest for developing better methods for the removal of mercury from aqueous solutions. Every method suffers from one or the other drawback. We now report an efficient method of removal of

chloride, followed by the separation and determination of mercury at trace level by extraction with ethylacetate. The suitability of the method for the removal of mercury from effluent samples of chlor-alkali industry has been verified.

Experimental

Materials: A stock solution (mg ml⁻¹) of mercuric chloride was prepared and diluted appropriately. The tracer ²⁰³Hg in the form of solution of mercuric nitrate in nitric acid was supplied by B.A.R.C., Bombay. Ethylacetate was used after purification by distillation. All other chemicals used were sufficiently pure.

Effluent samples from a chlor-alkali industry situated in Andhra Pradesh, were collected from different spots. Care was taken not to introduce excessive air into the samples.

Equipment: An E.C.I.L. S.C. 604 single channel analyser coupled with a 3" well type scintillation detector and an E.C.I.L. M.A. 5800A mercury analyser were used.

Procedure for extraction of mercury: 15 ml of the aqueous phase containing 45000 counts for 50 ml⁻¹ of mercury tracer and appropriate concentrations of mercury at 35° was extracted briskly for 5 min with an equal volume of ethylacetate in a 60 ml separatory funnel. After allowing for 10 min the layers were separated and analysed using scintillation counter.

Procedure for the estimation of mercury in effluents: The pH of the effluent was adjusted to 2-3 and the chloride content in the sample was initially determined by potentiometric titration using silver nitrate. Stoichiometric amounts of the solution of lead acetate (20%) containing glacial acetic acid (1%) and sodium fluoride (1%) solutions were added to the effluent and stirred well. The resultant precipitate (PbClF) was allowed to digest on a water bath for 1 h. The precipitate was filtered through a sintered glass crucible, washed several times with saturated lead acetate solution and water. The filtrate was transferred into a 250 ml volumetric flask and made up to the mark with water. Mercury was extracted with ethylacetate¹ and its content assayed.

Results and Discussion

The mechanism of the extraction of mercury from aqueous solutions with ethylacetate is through the formation of a solvated species of the type HgCl₂.2S (S=ethylacetate^{1,2}). Using the standard procedure for the extraction¹, the pertinent variables such as pH, chloride concentration and extractant, were studied and the optimum conditions for the extraction were determined.

The results on the study of interferences show that the tolerance of diverse ions is fairly good. Since chloride is a serious interference in the

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